

AUTHENTIC LEARNING ACTIVITIES IN TECHNOLOGY AND LIVELIHOOD EDUCATION FOR AN ENHANCED STUDENTS' PERFORMANCE IN COOKERY

GEMMALYN LAGUNERO SANTIAGO¹

ZENAIDA M. CUENCA, MAT²

gemmalyn.santiago@deped.gov.ph¹

zmmcuenca@gmail.com²

ORCID No. 0000-0002-4622-6676

Laguna State Polytechnic University, San Pablo City Campus, San Pablo Laguna, Philippines

ABSTRACT

The study sought to develop authentic learning activities in Grade 10 Cookery to determine its relationship with the performance of eighty-five (85) grade 10 students from Santo Tomas Integrated National High School, Calauan, Laguna enrolled during school year 2020-2021. Frequency and percentage were used to determine demographics; Mean and standard deviation was employed to quantify the level of acceptability and perception of the learning activities, approaches and overall features. Pearson-moment correlation coefficient, (r) were utilized to determine the correlation between the level of authenticity of enriched teacher-made learning activities in cookery and the performance of Grade 10 TLE students. An authentic learning activity were crafted, evaluated and validated by experts prior to field testing and made use of survey questionnaire to measure respondents' perception and the summative test for the level of performance. Study shows most of the respondents are female, 16 years of age, interested and assume high cookery skills with overall acceptable perception of the features, parts and learning approaches of the authentic learning material as acceptable. However, obtained low mastery achievement for knowledge and skills and average mastery for character. Lastly, the authentic learning activities and the level of performance of grade 10 students in TLE-Cookery is not significantly related as revealed by Pearson Moment Correlation (r) value of less than zero.

Keywords: Authentic Learning Activities, Level of Performance, Relationship